

Predictor variable	Median				95% Confidence Interval				Pairwise Comparisons			
	C1	C2	C3	C4	C1	C2	C3	C4	C1	C2	C3	C4
nr-sprints	13	15	14	11	[17.28, 18.89]	[19.4, 22.6]	[18.62, 21.44]	[15.43, 16.80]				*
out-degree	7	3	4	4	[7.33, 8.01]	[3.09, 3.70]	[3.54, 4.96]	[4.06, 5.60]	*			
hist-performance	0.69	0.67	0.74	0.61	[0.68, 0.71]	[0.63, 0.65]	[0.69, 0.72]	[0.58, 0.62]				
dev-age-abc	2.49	2.61	2.92	2.84	[2.45, 2.59]	[2.53, 2.65]	[2.79, 2.93]	[2.74, 2.96]				
team-existence	1.30	1.53	1.29	1.42	[1.48, 1.54]	[1.75, 1.84]	[1.51, 1.63]	[1.78, 1.89]				
team-size	8	7	6	7	[7.08, 8.06]	[6.99, 7.24]	[5.95, 6.41]	[7.14, 7.86]			*	
security-level	0.56	0.77	0.53	0.36	[0.51, 0.61]	[0.74, 0.80]	[0.47, 0.59]	[0.24, 0.48]		*		*
unplanned-stories	0.11	0.16	0.10	0.08	[0.09, 0.12]	[0.15, 0.17]	[0.08, 0.12]	[0.05, 0.11]		*		
changed-leads	3	2	3	2	[2.46, 2.54]	[2.47, 2.55]	[2.92, 3.08]	[1.41, 1.59]				*
stability-ratio	0.73	0.81	0.64	0.72	[0.71, 0.75]	[0.79, 0.82]	[0.62, 0.67]	[0.68, 0.76]		*		
nr-stories	52	43	39	45	[73.20, 80.83]	[64.24, 72.81]	[59.65, 72.15]	[67.10, 74.18]	*			
nr-incidents	8	12	8	6	[5.11, 10.90]	[10.30, 15.72]	[7.45, 10.64]	[5.26, 8.74]		*		
dev-workload	15	12	10	8	[12.80, 14.62]	[11.65, 12.73]	[9.32, 12.55]	[6.11, 9.89]	*			*
BRE	0.23	0.17	0.11	0.09	[0.24, 0.26]	[0.20, 0.22]	[0.12, 0.15]	[0.09, 0.12]	*	*	*	*

TABLE 2: Characteristics of delay profile clusters: Cluster 1 (C1), Cluster 2 (C2), Cluster 3 (C3), Cluster 4 (C4). * indicates that a cluster is significantly different from all other clusters for the corresponding predictor variable (pairwise Wilcoxon tests with Bonferroni correction).